

Table 1. Variations in total chlorophyll content in 3 cultivars under different temperature regimes. West Bengal, India.^a

Variety	30 DS			60 DS			90 DS		
	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	Visual rating	Min temp (°C)	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	Visual rating	Min temp (°C)	Total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	Visual rating	Min temp (°C)
CNM20	0.79	1		0.35	7		0.48	7	
G.S. 10231	0.87	1	22.3	0.75	1	17.5	0.49	1	13.7
IR8	0.98	1		1.18	3		0.51	5	
Mean	0.88			0.75			0.49		
CNM20	0.79	1		0.23	7		0.59	7	
G.S. 10231	0.71	1	18.6	0.48	1	14.4	0.68	1	9.5
IR8	0.87	1		0.37	3		0.48	5	
Mean	0.79			0.36			0.58		
CNM20	0.35	3		0.23	7		0.59	7	
G.S. 10231	0.42	1	16.4	0.43	3	12.6	0.66	3	11.2
IR8	0.25	3		0.21	5		0.58	3	
Mean	0.34			0.29			0.61		
CNM20	0.37	7		0.23	7		0.58	3	
G.S. 10231	0.38	3	9.1	0.82	3	12.0	0.84	1	14.7
IR8	0.22	7		0.77	5		0.48	3	
Mean	0.32			0.60			0.63		

^aDS = days after sowing. Visual rating scale: 1 = least or no yellowing, 3 = slight yellowing, 5 = moderate yellowing, and 7 = severe yellowing.

Table 2. Differences in chlorophyll a-b ratio under different temperature regimes.^a

Sowing	30 DS			60 DS			90 DS		
	Mean total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	ca:cb	Mean min temp (°C)	Mean total Chlorophyll Content (mg/g fresh wt)	ca:cb	Mean min. temp (°C)	Mean total chlorophyll content (mg/g fresh wt)	ca:cb	Mean min. temp (°C)
7 Oct	0.88	0.97	22.3	0.75	0.98	17.5	0.49	1.36	13.7
22 Oct	0.79	0.72	18.6	0.36	1.32	14.4	0.58	1.24	9.5
7 Nov	0.34	1.53	16.4	0.29	1.25	12.6	0.61	1.19	11.2
22 Nov	0.32	1.32	9.1	0.60	1.35	12.0	0.63	1.20	14.7

^aDS = days after sowing.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Morphological and serological similarities of rice ragged stunt virus samples from China and the Philippines

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The occurrence of rice ragged stunt disease has been reported in China, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Philippines,

Sri Lanka, Taiwan, and Thailand. The disease symptoms are similar in various countries: stunting of plants, appearance of ragged and twisted leaves, formation of vein-swellings, delay in flowering, production of nodal branches, incomplete emergence of panicles, and panicles bearing mostly unfilled grains. The transmission of rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV) by the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* in a persistent manner is also similar.

An early report [IRRN 4(2):12, 1979] noted that the antiserum of RRSV prepared from materials mailed to Italy

from the Philippines reacted positively to diseased materials collected in India, Indonesia, and Thailand when tested by immunoelectron microscopy using the decoration technique.

Recently, diseased materials collected in Guangdong, China [IRRN 4(6): 10, 1979], were examined under an electron microscope and tested by the immunoelectron microscopic techniques of trapping and decoration, and by the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA). The antiserum used was prepared with RRSV from the Philippines. Electron microscopy

revealed isometric particles about 50 nm in diameter having spikes, but no other virus-like particles. The RRSV-like particles from China reacted positively with the antiserum of RRSV from the Philippines in both the immunoelectron microscopy and ELISA. We concluded that the rice ragged stunt disease in China is caused by a virus morphologically and serologically similar to that in the Philippines. ■

Report of 1978 Rice Tungro Virus Collaborative Project

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The life span and tungro transmission of viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* on seedlings of 10 rice varieties were collaboratively studied at the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project (AICRIP), the Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, India, the IRRI, and Lembaga Penelitian Pertanian (LPP), Indonesia. The objective was to use the varieties as differentials for determining the existence of biotypes of the tungro vector and strains of the tungro virus.

On the basis of life span, the ability of the tungro vector to attack the 10 varieties was similar at the 4 locations. The test varieties were unable to separate the biotypes of the tungro vector in the four locations. The arbitrary classification based on average life span placed Gam Pai 30-12-15, IR34, and Ptb 18 in the resistant group; Latisail and Pankhari 203 in the intermediate group; and Ambemohar 159, Habiganj DW8, IR26, Kataribhog, and TN1 in the susceptible group. However, Ambemohar 159 was in the intermediate group at AICRIP but in the susceptible group at the other locations. Pankhari 203 was susceptible at CRRI, but intermediate at the other locations (see table). Hence, these two varieties could be used to show the slight difference in tungro vector biotypes between AICRIP and CRRI.

On the basis of tungro transmission and seedling infection, the averages

Reactions of 10 rice varieties to tungro-viruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* and to tungro virus on the basis of an arbitrary classification system at 4 locations, 1978.

Variety	Reaction ^a to vector (left letter) and virus (right)				
	AICRIP	CKRI	IRRI	LPP	Mean
TN1	SS	SS	SS	SS	SS
IR26	SI	SS	SS	SS	SS
Ambemohar 159	IS	SI	SI	SI	SI
Habiganj DW8	SS	SR	SR	SR	SR
Kataribhog	II	SR	SR	SR	SR
Latisail	II	SS	SS	SI	IS
Pankhari 203	II	SI	IR	IR	IR
IR34	II	IS	RS	II	RS
Gam Pai 30-1 2-15	RI	IR	RI	II	RI
Ptb 18	IS	RR	RI	RI	RI

^aK, I, and S indicate resistant, intermediate, and susceptible. The underscoring indicates striking difference from others.

support the arbitrary classification of Habiganj DW8, Pankhari 203, and Kataribhog in the group resistant to the tungro virus; Ambemohar 159, Gam Pai 30-12-15, and Ptb 18 in the intermediate group; and IR26, IR34, Latisail, and TN1 in the susceptible group (see table). However, variations occurred among the locations, particularly at AICRIP where none of the varieties could be put in the resistant group. Habiganj DW8

was susceptible at AICRIP but resistant at the other locations. Ptb 18, also susceptible at AICRIP, was resistant or intermediate at the other locations. Hence, the strain of the rice tungro virus at AICRIP might be more virulent. Habiganj DW8 and Ptb 18 could be used to separate the tungro strain at AICRIP (if it remains stable) from strains at other locations. ■

Perpetuation of rice tungro virus and its vectors

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The possibility that improved rice cultivars, stubble, wild rices, weeds, and cereal crops can act as reservoir host for rice tungro virus and that wild rices, weeds, and cereal crops are host for the tungro virus *Nephotettix virescens* and *N. nigropictus* was investigated. Both standing crops and stubble of the cultivars Bala, IR8, Krishna, Padma, and TN1 served as better sources of virus inoculum. The cultivars that served as poor inoculum sources were IR20, IR30, Annapurna, IR26, Ratna, CR 138-802-10, and CR 138-994-27.

The susceptible wild rice species were *Oryza australiensis*, *O. barthii*, *O. brachyantha*, *O. eichingeri*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, and *O. perennis*. Of these *O. barthii*, *O. nivara*, and *O. glaberrima* served as better sources of

virus inoculum than the others when tested at 15, 30, 35, 60, 75, and 90 days after inoculation (see table).

The resistant wild rice species were *O. alta*, *O. grandiglumis*, *O. latifolia*, *O. malampzhuensis*, *O. minuta*, *O. officinalis*, *O. perreiri*, and *O. schwenforthiana*. None of the 20 weed species and 6 cereal crops tested was susceptible to tungro virus.

The vector species *N. nigropictus* had a broader spectrum of host range than *N. virescens*. *N. nigropictus* could reproduce in *O. eichingeri*, *O. glaberrima*, *O. malampzhuensis*, *O. minuta*, *O. nivara*, *O. officinales*, *O. perennis*, *O. punctata*, *O. sativa*, *Echinochloa colonurn*, *Ischaemum indicum*, *Leersia hexandra*, and *Paspalum orbiculare*. *N. virescens* could reproduce in *O. glaberrima*, *O. nivara*, *O. perennis*, *O. sativa*, *E. colonum*, and *P. orbiculare*.

Intensive cultivation of semidwarf rice cultivars has made the overlapping of two crops of rice a common practice. Such circumstances might cause greater